

DEMOGRAPHIC PROCESSES AND THE LABOR MARKET IMPROVING
INTERCONNECTION

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Abstract: Comprehensive scientific research aimed at developing the impact of demographic processes on the labor market in the world based on statistical analysis, including the impact of the demographic situation on the labor market, the impact of demographic processes on the regional economy, demographic changes on labor supply and economic growth. Scientific research is being conducted in areas such as the effect on swelling. Based on these aspects, conducting scientific research on the statistical study of demographic processes and the interaction of the labor market is one of the urgent issues. This article addresses this and can be used by undergraduates, graduate students, independent researchers, and a wide audience.

Keywords: demography, economic crisis, statistics, labor market, demographic situation, demographic development.

Introduction. According to world statistics, 197.7 million people in the world are currently unemployed despite being healthy and able to work. This number itself means to observe a person and take into account many factors when making a plan for the future. It can be said that important decisions are made in the management of demographic situations in the world, as well as in professions such as job creation, planning of infrastructure, construction, education, and medical facilities. However, in the practice of economic and statistical research, little attention is paid to studying the relationship between demographic processes and the labor market. To conduct a comprehensive statistical study in our country, it is necessary to study demographic factors, as well as their impact on the labor market and the population in detail. In 2017-2021, the strategy of Action on the five priority areas of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "creating new jobs and ensuring the employment of the population, first of all, graduates of secondary specialized and higher educational institutions, ensuring the balance of the labor market and infrastructure development, reducing the unemployment rate; important tasks of creating conditions for the full implementation of labor and entrepreneurial activity of the able-bodied population, improving the quality of the workforce, expanding the system of professional training, retraining and upgrading of skills of persons in need of work." Effective implementation of these tasks requires studying the interdependence of demographic processes and the labor market in our republic.

The level of study of the problem. Issues related to demographic processes and labor resources. Researched in-depth scientific works of foreign economists such as Raymer, S. Coles, and S. Markusen.

Issues of statistical analysis of demographic processes and the study of sources of formation of the labor market from CIS scientists I.Yeliseyeva, N.Varshavskaya, V.Chumarina, A.Kvasha, A.Andryunin, A.Korovkin, K.Parbuzin, N.Vargin, A.Osipov, Bruy, Ye. Kurilina, M.Sonin, and others have taken a large place in scientific research.

The issues of statistical study of demographic processes and the interaction of the labor market have been the subject of scientific research by the economists of our republic. In particular, the scientific research of famous economists of our country K. Abdurakhmanov, B. Khodiyev, T. Shodiyev, N.

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Zokirova, O. Atamirzayev, D. Karimova, B. Umurzakov, R. Ubaidullayeva, L. Maksakova, B. Usmanov, L. Shaylar issues of modeling, forecasting and analysis of demographic processes and the labor market in Uzbekistan were comprehensively researched.

The main part. According to the definition of Ye.A. Kechina: "Demographic process" is a sequence of the same events that are important for the change of generations in people's lives. The next definition that needs to be clarified is "demographic development".

According to VSSsteshenko: "Demographic development is the maintenance of population size as a result of historical development."

In addition to the opinions of the above-mentioned scientists, we offer the following definitions:

- ✓ **demographic process** - mechanical (migration) or natural (birth, death, marriage, and divorce) movement of the population;
- ✓ **demographic development** is a transition from progressive and regressive to stationary types of population change;
- ✓ **demographic growth** - an increase in the population at a certain time and in a certain place.

Demographic processes affect the economy, primarily by changing the quality and quantity of labor resources. The number of working-age population changes mainly due to natural growth. The statistical study of the quality of the working population is more complicated than the study of their number because several factors affect this indicator.

According to forecasts from the World Health Organization, by 2030, 8 percent of the population of Uzbekistan will be people aged 65 and over.

Demographic growth in Uzbekistan in 2010-2020 was 1.4-1.8% per year, only in 2012 this indicator was 3.9%. This situation was determined in 2011 based on the data of a sample survey covering 10% of the population (Table 1). Demographic growth in Uzbekistan is average by world standards (less than 1% is a low indicator; more than 2.5% is a high indicator). **Table 1**

Demographic and economic growth rate in Uzbekistan in 2010-2020 (compared to the previous year, in percent)

No	Indicators	2010 _	2012 _	2014 _	2016 _	2018 _	20 20
1.	Demographic growth	101.7	101.5	103.9	101.4	101.7	101.5
2.	GDP growth	108.5	108.3	108.2	108.0	108.1	105.3
3.	Economic growth	106.7	106.7	104.1	106.5	106.3	103.8

The main task of the statistical study of the relationship between demographic processes and the labor market in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to analyze and evaluate the dynamics of the population and the specific characteristics of the population structure. After all, the development of the country's labor potential occurs precisely under the influence of demographic factors.

In the conditions of the market economy in Uzbekistan, the role of demographic factors in the formation of the labor market is increasing, and it is becoming more relevant. The demographic trends observed in our country are not only the result of the demographic situation in the early 1990s (high birth rate, the tradition of large families, mass social protection for families) but also the result of socio-economic processes that took place during the years of independence.

Statistical analysis of the relationship between demographic processes and the labor market includes:

quantitative factors - population dynamics, death, birth, migration, etc.;

qualitative factors - population's gender, age, level of education, etc content on.

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The assessment of population dynamics includes the analysis of natural growth (the difference between the number of births and deaths in a certain period) and mechanical growth (the difference between the number of immigrants and those who emigrated). The overall increase in the number of the population was fully supported by natural growth (a stable increase in the number of emigrants compared to those who immigrated could not have a serious negative effect on it).

Determining the causes of the modern dynamics of natural movement is important for the assessment of the demographic future, demographic policy, and measures affecting the process of population development. In this case, it is necessary to clarify the issue of which factors have a greater influence on the dynamics of the modern population, that is, a sharp decrease in the number of births (as a result of structural factors, including changes in the reproductive tendency) or an increase in the number of deaths.

Major socio-economic changes that took place in the 90s of the 20th century affected all areas of human activity, including the demographic situation. In addition to the natural movement of the population, an important factor affecting the number and composition of the population is migration. At each stage of economic development, migration makes it possible to achieve a dynamic balance between demand and supply, taking into account the specific placement of labor resources in the regions of the country, taking into account the qualitative characteristics of the workforce.

In our opinion, migration cannot be evaluated as a positive or negative phenomenon. On the one hand, the increase in the number of departures will ease the tension in the labor market, and on the other hand, it will lead to a shortage of labor force, which is an important factor in economic growth.

Population age composition is the ratio of different age groups. To analyze the age and gender composition of the population, a graphical method called the age-sex pyramid is widely used. In the age structure of the population of Uzbekistan, there were many young people under the age of 15. It has changed due to the declining birth rate. Although those born in the 1980s and 1990s passed into the group of working-age people (labor resources), the age structure of the population today, according to the classification of the Swedish demographer AG. Sundberg belongs to the progressive type of population re-emergence.

Conclusion. There is a system of independent indicators to describe the state of demographic processes and employment of the population, and complex system analysis requires the use of a system of independent, local, and integrated indicators that are related to each other. Therefore, when analyzing both social and economic aspects, it is recommended to use mixed models that include statistical methods to solve them. Along with the chain replacement methods and the correlation-regression relationship, it is necessary to use the variation series and the ranking estimation method. After all, during the complex analysis, not only the data on the country but also the indicators on the regions (regions) are important.

List of used literature:

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